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Vaccine Hesitancy: The Growing Treat to public health

Abstract

The World Health Organization (WHO) identified vaccine hesitancy (VH) as one of the top 10 global health issues in 2019. We discuss the causes of VH, how it hinders vaccine uptake and prevents the development of collective immunity, and potential remedies. The safety and effectiveness of vaccines are still up for debate, which encourages VH and erodes public trust in vaccination. WHO has created survey questionnaires and behavioral and social drivers (BeSD) tools that nations can use to determine the causes of low childhood COVID-19 vaccine uptake and to develop national vaccination campaigns to dispel these myths.

Keywords:

Vaccine hesitancy, COVID-19, Pandemic, Influenza, Review.

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), vaccine hesitancy is a behavior that is impacted by a variety of factors, such as complacency (do not see

the need for a vaccine, do not value the vaccine), convenience (access), and confidence (do not trust the vaccine or provider). A diverse collection of people who are unsure about certain vaccines or vaccinations in general are known as vaccine-hesitant people. Vaccine-hesitant people can accept all vaccines but still be worried about them, reject or postpone some immunizations but accept others, or reject all vaccines.

A group of patients in December 2019 had pneumonia brought on by an unidentified disease connected to Wuhan, China's seafood wholesale industry. The entire genome of patient samples was then sequenced, which led to the discovery of a new coronavirus. The International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses' Coronavirus Study Group dubbed it severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). The WHO named the virus-caused illness coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). The virus first infected and killed thousands of people in China before spreading to Italy, other European nations, and the United States, where the number of verified new cases is currently rising daily. The high rate of infection and extensive infectivity led the WHO to proclaim it a pandemic. To prevent the pandemic, a lot of work has gone into creating COVID-19 vaccines, and the majority of these vaccine candidates have used the S-protein of SARS-CoV-2.

To prevent COVID-19, three vaccinations are now approved and advised. Other COVID-19 vaccines in the US are also undergoing or planning extensive (phase 3) clinical studies. Vaccinating people, especially healthcare workers, is essential since the availability of vaccinations is the primary factor in reducing the number of new diseases. However, additional research focusing on HPV and HIV vaccine trials in the US and Europe have shown that vaccination willingness is significantly influenced, particularly by mistrust of health authorities.

Depending on the severity of the controversies and the burden of the COVID-19 pandemic's health and socioeconomic effects, the global crisis may have a more or less significant effect on public trust in public health authorities, science, and medicine in different countries. The novelty of the disease and worries about the safety and effectiveness of the vaccine have caused a significant percentage of Americans to express reluctance to receive the COVID-19 vaccine, in addition to a segment of the population that opposes vaccinations.

However, this phenomenon has also been observed elsewhere. In May 2020, approximately 25% of respondents to five surveys conducted in France (representing representative samples of 1000 adults) said they would have declined a future vaccine against it if it had been made available. This was primarily because of safety concerns regarding a vaccine created in an emergency. Therefore, our study's goal was to better understand and examine the issue of vaccine reluctance during the COVID-19 pandemic, with an emphasis on vaccine hesitancy toward the COVID-19 vaccination, through a narrative review.

Percentage of vaccine acceptance

Only in an Italian trial (Barello et al.) did 86.1% of participants (students) opt to receive the COVID-19 vaccine, indicating that vaccine acceptability was not very high. When the general population was taken into account, the percentage of respondents who said they would probably or definitely accept the COVID-19 vaccine dropped to a high of 77.6% (Detoc et al.). The percentages did not vary significantly, despite the fact that each study was carried out at a different time.

The situation is similar for influenza vaccine alone: Grech et al.'s study reported the highest percentage of acceptance (69%), but Goldman et al.'s study, which was the only one that focused solely on influenza vaccine, revealed that only 54.3% of parents were in favor of vaccinating their children and 58.3% intended to vaccinate themselves.

Participants' motivations and influencing factors for declining the immunization
The following is a summary of the factors that affected the decision to receive the immunizations (or not):

- Ethnicity: African Americans and Black people were less accepted
- Employment status: those without jobs were less accepted
- Personal belief: Participants who personally believed that vaccines were harmful had lower acceptance, but those who had previously received vaccinations, particularly those for influenza, had better acceptance.
- Religion: there was a negative correlation between religiosity and the COVID-19 vaccine.

- Politics (!): According to Kreps et al., respondents who indicated that they were Democratic were substantially more likely to decide to be vaccinated. People were much more likely to refuse the vaccine if they felt close to radical parties or if they did not vote or did not feel close to any party (Ward et al.). Refusing vaccination was more common among those who supported far-left or far-right candidates in the most recent elections (COCONEL Group). Pogue et al. found no correlation between vaccination attitudes and political ideology.
 - Gender: Women were less accepted.
- Education (!): participants with less education were less likely to be accepted (with the exception of the study by Salali et al. in Turkey).
 - Age (!): a lower willingness to accept immunization was linked to a lower age. With the exception of Palamenghi et al.'s study, which found that middle-aged individuals were less likely to be vaccinated than those between the ages of 18 and 34 and those over 60. Additionally, the COCONEL group found that people over 75 had more reluctance.
- Income (!): Participants' acceptance was lower when their income was lower. Pogue et al. found no correlation between vaccination attitudes and income.
- COVID-19 infection: there is no discernible difference between infected and non-infected individuals.
- Fear of contracting COVID-19: People who were really afraid of contracting the virus were less likely to decline the vaccination.
- Employment in healthcare environments (!): employees in the healthcare industry were more accepted. With the exception of Dror et al.'s study, which found no distinction in vaccine uptake between healthcare and non-healthcare workers. Additionally, Barelllo et al. found no discernible variations between healthcare students.

(!) = This symbol is used to draw attention to elements that provide contradictory findings.

The most frequently cited reasons for refusing vaccinations were general anti-vaccine sentiment, safety concerns or the belief that a hurriedly produced vaccine

is too dangerous, the belief that the vaccine is useless due to the harmless nature of COVID-19, a general lack of trust, doubts about the vaccine's effectiveness, the belief that one is already immunized, and doubts about the vaccine's provenance.

Discussion

Our review highlighted an overall high vaccine hesitancy toward the COVID-19 vaccine, but also toward influenza vaccine. These results are not surprising: studies around the world on vaccine hesitancy, in general, showed prevalence ranging from 8% to 15%. However, it should be specified that the speed of the pandemic and the considered time span (up to November 2020) could make our results not totally representative of the real situation.

One of the most interesting aspects of the review is the point-to-point analysis of factors that influenced the acceptance or refusal. This represents, however, an Instantaneous photography of the actual situation: in fact, as Williams et al. reported, although the reasons why parents chose to delay or refuse vaccines for their children have been thoroughly examined, the reasons for vaccine delay or refusal may change over time.

In our review black or African people had a lower acceptance rate. This datum is in line with another study that showed that among African Americans, there was a higher degree of skepticism and concern about the flu vaccine.

Our review highlighted that unemployed people and those with a lower income had a lower acceptance rate; however, Pogue et al. observed that income had no relationship with the attitude toward vaccination. In addition, participants with low education had a lower acceptance rate (except for the study conducted in Turkey by Salali et al.). These data are partially in line with what reported by Danis et al.: their study revealed how economic hardship represented a determinant of vaccine hesitancy, while no association was found between economic hardship and vaccine refusal. On the other hand, the lower education of both mother and father was a valid predictor of refusal of all vaccines, while hesitancy seemed to not be affected by parental education.

In another survey although caregivers from households in the 3rd or 4th quintiles were more likely to fully immunize their children than those in the other quintiles,

this was not statistically significant. Our findings showed that a higher level of education seemed to be a protective factor against refusing vaccines. However, there was no consensus about this association in other studies, some being in contrast, in accordance or showing no significant association. Parents with a higher-education background may use selected sources of information, relying on a critical-thinking attitude and making more active choices. In our review, we observed that religiosity was negatively correlated with COVID-19 vaccination. This particular aspect has already been described by other authors which observed that some people avoided vaccination based on religious grounds including religious explanations (“God did not take any medicine”) or associating vaccines with Satanism.

The Impact of political ideology on vaccination acceptance or refusal is one of the most intriguing aspects of our review. Those who identified as Democratic were significantly more likely to choose vaccination; those who felt close to radical parties or did not vote or did not feel close to any party were significantly more likely to refuse vaccination; and those who voted for far-left or far-right candidates in the most recent French elections were more likely to refuse vaccination. Kennedy et al. have already carried out this type of analysis.

With an emphasis on populist parties: they noted that, at least in the Western European context, support for populist parties could be used as a stand-in for vaccine hesitancy, and that a rise in support would indicate that public health actors should exercise caution.

Women were less likely to be accepted, according to our review. This statistic is consistent with other research that discovered that a significant portion of women expressed worries about vaccine safety and a lack of confidence in the accuracy and objectivity of information given by medical professionals.

In our review, we observed three apparently independent phenomena:

- 1) low age was associated to a lower willingness to receive vaccination;
- 2) those who were highly concerned about being infected were less likely to refuse the vaccine;
- 3) no difference observed between those who have been infected and those who have not. It is important to remember that risk perception is an important factor

influencing risk behaviors and people with lower risk perception tend to take risk behaviors or reduce preventive behaviors.

Young people (such as college students as reported by Ding et al.) are usually healthy, and often have mild symptoms after being infected with COVID-19, which can have a significant impact on the spread of COVID-19. It is therefore possible that they may have a tendency to refuse vaccinations due to a limited perception of the risk; therefore, as Ding et al. suggest, it is necessary to improve college students' perceptions of risk through various forms of health education, and some students with low risk perceptions should receive special attention.

There were mixed findings regarding vaccine acceptance among healthcare workers. While healthcare workers generally had higher acceptance, Dror et al. found no difference in vaccine acceptance between healthcare and non-healthcare personnel, and Barello et al. found no significant differences between healthcare students and non-healthcare students.

Found no discernible variations across healthcare students. The European Centre for Disease Control has conducted a thorough investigation into the issue of vaccine hesitancy among healthcare professionals, finding that these professionals indicated a lack of faith in health authorities and were concerned about the dangers associated with vaccination. Some medical professionals opposed vaccinations in general as well.

The following were the most common reasons given for refusing vaccinations: general anti-vaccine sentiment, safety concerns or the belief that a hurriedly produced vaccine is too dangerous, the belief that the vaccine is useless due to the harmless nature of COVID-19, a general lack of trust, doubts about the vaccine's effectiveness, the belief that one is already immunized, and doubts about the vaccine's provenance. These evidences are quite in line with what reported in other studies. For example, Pugliese-Garcia et al. reported in their survey the respondents' fear of being injected incorrectly or contracting infections, of the fear of pain.

Perceptions of vaccine effectiveness were often built in misconceptions about how, for whom and for how long immunizations function. Respondents believed that vaccines worked against illnesses, particularly for childhood illness, rather than being disease-specific. Conversely, Alabbad et al. found that the most frequent

justification for vaccine refusal was the conviction that the vaccine was unneeded and had no beneficial effects.

In their interviews with parents and medical professionals, Krishnamoorthy et al. found that the main cause of the reluctance was the false information about the vaccine's safety that circulated on social media. They have stated that without verifying the veracity of the information, the message was shared around friends, family, and other community members. Nonetheless, recurring awareness campaigns across different mass media platforms have aided in the removal of these obstacles.

Some participants in certain research even favored non-formal, conventional, and religious methods of treatment and prevention. In addition to the informal and traditional options including traditional brews, herbs, and tattoos, participants reported instances of young men using beer, spirits, and local alcohol, Tujilijili, Junta, and Kachasu.

Conclusion

Even during the COVID-19 epidemic, vaccination reluctance is still prevalent, and there are a number of reasons why people refuse to get vaccines. Growing hesitation causes coverage to decline and frequently precedes an infectious disease outbreak, making this phenomena a significant issue. To encourage patients and assist in making educated vaccination decisions, healthcare professionals—particularly pediatricians and general practitioners—should be involved. Nevertheless, even though researchers have started to create and assess interventions for vaccine-hesitant individuals (particularly parents), the available data does not prove that one approach is more successful than another; thus, more work is required to develop and assess interventions.

Reference

1. Group, T.S.V.H.W . 2013. What influences vaccine acceptance: a model of determinants of vaccine hesitancy. [Google Scholar]
2. Zhou M.Y., et al. From SARS to COVID-19: what we have learned about children infected with COVID-19. *Int J Infect Dis.* 2020;96:710–714. Doi: 10.1016/j.ijid.2020.04.090. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

3. Gorbalenya A.E., B S.C., Baric R.S., de Groot R.J., Drosten C., Gulyaeva A.A. 2020. Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus: the species and its viruses – a statement of the Coronavirus Study Group. [Google Scholar]
4. CDC . 2021. Different COVID-19 vaccines. <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/vaccines/differentvaccines.html> Updated Jan. 15, 2021. 28/01/2021]; Available from. [Google Scholar]
5. Verger P., Dube E. Restoring confidence in vaccines in the COVID-19 era. *Expert Rev Vaccines*. 2020;1–3. Doi: 10.1080/14760584.2020.1825945. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
6. Fisher K.A., et al. Attitudes toward a potential SARS-CoV-2 vaccine: a survey of U.S. Adults. *Ann Intern Med*. 2020 Dec;173(12):964–973. Doi: 10.7326/M203569. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
7. Palamenghi L., et al. Mistrust in biomedical research and vaccine hesitancy: the forefront challenge in the battle against COVID-19 in Italy. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 2020;35(8):785–788. Doi: 10.1007/s10654-020-00675-8. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
8. Dror A.A., et al. Vaccine hesitancy: the next challenge in the fight against COVID-19. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 2020;35(8):775–779. Doi: 10.1007/s10654-02000671-y. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
9. Barello S., et al. ‘Vaccine hesitancy’ among university students in Italy during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 2020;35(8):781–783. Doi: 10.1007/s10654-020-00670-z. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
10. Giambi C., et al. Parental vaccine hesitancy in Italy – results from a national survey. *Vaccine*. 2018;36(6):779–787. Doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2017.12.074. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

